

Thermodynamic properties of ethyl acrylate with higher primary alkane-1-ols at 298.15 and 308.15 K temperatures

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Abstract : Thermodynamic properties including density, viscosity and ultrasonic velocity of the binary liquid mixture of ethyl acrylate with higher primary alkane-1-ols namely hexane-1-ol, heptane-1-ol, octane-1-ol and decane-1-ol have been measured over entire range of composition, at 298.15 and 308.15 K temperatures and at atmospheric pressure. These parameters were used in the recently proposed Jouyban-Acree model. These basic properties were used to calculate excess properties like excess molar volume (V^E), deviation in viscosity ($\Delta\eta$) and deviation in isentropic compressibility (κ^E_s). The excess properties further have been fitted to the Redlich-Kister polynomial equation. The mixture viscosities were correlated by Grunberg-Nissan, Tamura and Kurata, McAllister three and four body model equations. Ultrasonic velocities of these binary liquid mixtures were used to calculate intermolecular free length as well as available volume.

Keywords : Ethyl acrylate + alkane-1-ols, Jouyban-Acree model, excess molar volume, Grunberg-Nissan equation.

Introduction

Properties of liquid-liquid binary mixtures are thermodynamically very important as a part of studies of thermodynamic, acoustic and transport aspects. The compositional dependence of thermodynamic properties has proved to be a very useful tool in understanding nature and extent of pattern of molecular aggregation resulting from intermolecular interactions between components. It is a powerful means of characterizing various aspects of physicochemical behavior of liquid mixture and studying interactions between molecules. Mixing volume effects are also important from both theoretical as well as practical point of view. Above phenomenon is of significance in many practical applications mainly in paints, varnishes and printing ink industries where volume effects are also involved in conversion of formulations from gravimetric to volumetric analysis.

Density and viscosity are important fundamental properties for chemical design and optimization of chemical processes. They are also necessary for engineering calculations and research of mass, heat and fluid transfer. Ul-

trasonic velocity measured with great accuracy reflects degree of deviation from ideality. Deviations from ideal behavior have been widely used for study of structural variations and molecular interactions. In literature data exists for binary systems of ethyl ethanoate with ethyl acrylate, butyl acrylate, methyl methacrylate and styrene at 298.15 K¹, for volumetric behavior of acrylic esters with alkane-1-ols at 298.15 and 308.15 K², density and excess molar volume of the binary systems of dimethyl sulfoxide + ethyl acrylate, butyl acrylate, methyl methacrylate and styrene at 298.15 K³, volumetric properties of binary systems of dimethyl sulfoxide with methacrylic acid, vinyl acetate, butyl methacrylate and allyl methacrylate at 298.15 K⁴, volumetric properties of toluene with ethyl acrylate, butyl acrylate, methyl methacrylate, and styrene at 298.15 K⁵, thermodynamic properties of methyl methacrylate with alkoxyethanols and 1-alcohols at 298.15 and 308.15 K⁶, volumetric properties of ternary system 1,4-dioxane with butyl and ethyl acrylate and its binary at 298.15 K⁷, density and volume of mixing of ternary system ethyl benzene + styrene + ethyl

acrylate and its binaries at 298.15 K⁸, densities, excess volumes and partial molar volumes of *m*-xylene + ethyl acrylate + butyl acrylate + methyl methacrylate and + styrene at 298.15 K⁹, densities, sound speeds, excess volumes, excess isentropic compressibilities of methyl acrylate + 1-propanol or 1-butanol + hydrocarbons (*n*-hexane, *n*-heptane, cyclohexane, benzene, toluene) at 308.15 K¹⁰.

Experimental

Chemicals used in the present study were of analytical grade and supplied by S.D. Fine Chemicals Pvt., Mumbai (India) with quoted mass fraction purities : ethyl acrylate, EA (>0.998), hexane-1-ol (>0.997), heptane-1-ol (>0.995), octane-1-ol (>0.996) and decane-1-ol (>0.998). Prior to use all liquids were stored over 0.4 nm molecular sieves to reduce the water content and were degassed. In addition, ethyl acrylate was distilled before use. The binary mixtures of varying composition were prepared by mass in special air-tight bottles. The solutions of each composition were prepared fresh and all properties were measured the same day. The masses were recorded on a Mettler one pan balance, which can read up to fifth place of decimal, with an accuracy of ± 0.01 mg. Care was taken to avoid evaporation and contamination during mixing. The estimated uncertainty in mole fraction was $< 1 \times 10^{-4}$.

The densities of the solutions were measured using a single capillary pycnometer made of borosil glass with a bulb of 8 cm³ and capillary with internal diameter of 0.1 cm was chosen for present work. The details pertaining to calibration, experimental set up and operational procedure has been previously described. An average of triplicate measurement was taken in to account. The reproducibility of density measurement was $\pm 5 \times 10^{-5}$ g/cm³. The dynamic viscosities were measured using an Ubbelohde suspended level viscometer calibrated with conductivity water. An electronic digital stop watch with readability of ± 0.01 s was used for the flow time measurements. At least three repetitions of each data reproducible to ± 0.05 s were obtained, and the results were averaged. Since all flow times were greater than 300 s and capillary radius (0.1 mm) was far less than its length (50 to 60) mm, the kinetic energy and end corrections, respectively, were found to be negligible. The uncertain-

ties in dynamic viscosities are of the order of ± 0.003 mPa.s. The ultrasonic velocities were measured at a frequency of 2 MHz in these solutions by a single crystal ultrasonic interferometer (Mittal's F-81 model). The error in velocity measurements is $\pm 0.1\%$. The other experimental details are the same as reported earlier¹¹. A comparison of measured values of pure components with the literature values as presented in Table 1 shows a good agreement.

Table 1. Densities, ρ , viscosities, η , ultrasonic velocities, u , for pure components at $T = (298.15 \text{ and } 308.15) \text{ K}$

	$T = 298.15 \text{ K}$		$T = 308.15 \text{ K}$	
	Expt.	Lit.	Expt	Lit.
Ethyl acrylate				
ρ (g m ⁻³)	0.91632	0.91630 ²¹	0.90400	0.90460 ²¹
η (mPa.s)	0.518	0.517 ²¹	0.456	0.455 ²¹
u (m s ⁻¹)	1167	1167 ²²	1137	
Hexane-1-ol				
ρ (g m ⁻³)	0.81537	0.81510 ²³	0.80803	0.80810 ²³
η (mPa.s)	4.591	4.477 ²⁵	3.448	3.413 ²⁶
u (m s ⁻¹)	1306	1303 ²³	1274	1270 ²³
Heptane-1-ol				
ρ (g m ⁻³)	0.81871	0.81880 ²⁴	0.81251	0.81172 ²⁴
η (mPa.s)	5.725	5.770 ²⁵	4.322	4.266 ²⁶
u (m s ⁻¹)	1331	1327 ²⁴	1295	
Octane-1-ol				
ρ (g m ⁻³)	0.82160	0.82162 ²⁴	0.81453	0.81467 ²⁴
η (mPa.s)	7.362	7.363 ²⁵	5.520	5.250 ²⁶
u (m s ⁻¹)	1351	1347 ²⁴	1319	
Decane-1-ol				
ρ (g m ⁻³)	0.82630	0.82637 ²⁴	0.81944	0.81957 ²⁴
η (mPa.s)	11.793	11.790 ²⁵	8.116	8.124 ²⁶
u (m s ⁻¹)	1388	1379 ²⁴	1353	

Results and discussion

Twenty one density, viscosity and ultrasonic velocity measurements were performed with repetitions for four binary liquid systems namely ethyl acrylate (1) + hexane-1-ol (2), ethyl acrylate (1) + heptane-1-ol (2), ethyl acrylate (1) + octane-1-ol (2) and ethyl acrylate (1) + decane-1-ol (2) over the entire mole fraction range ($0 < x < 1$), at temperatures 298.15 and 308.15 K and at atmospheric pressure. Experimental values of densities (ρ), viscosities (η) and ultrasonic velocity (u) of these mixtures at $T = (298.15 \text{ and } 308.15) \text{ K}$ as a function of acrylic esters mole fraction are listed in Table 2.

Table 2. Densities, ρ , viscosities, η , ultrasonic velocities, u , for ethyl acrylate (1) + alkane-1-ol (2) at $T = (298.15 \text{ and } 308.15) \text{ K}$

x_1	$T = 298.15 \text{ K}$			$T = 308.15 \text{ K}$		
	ρ (g cm^{-3})	η (mPa.s)	u (m s^{-1})	ρ (g cm^{-3})	η (mPa.s)	u (m s^{-1})
	EA (1) + hexane-1-ol (2)					
0	0.81537	4.591	1306	0.80803	3.448	1274
0.0551	0.81984	4.071	1298	0.81238	3.085	1266
0.0998	0.82348	3.692	1291	0.81594	2.817	1260
0.1555	0.82815	3.270	1283	0.82049	2.517	1252
0.1998	0.83196	2.968	1277	0.82419	2.301	1245
0.2555	0.83685	2.629	1269	0.82892	2.056	1237
0.2999	0.84085	2.386	1263	0.83277	1.880	1231
0.3555	0.84597	2.114	1255	0.83770	1.680	1223
0.3999	0.85016	1.918	1248	0.84172	1.535	1217
0.4555	0.85552	1.699	1241	0.84685	1.372	1210
0.4999	0.85989	1.542	1235	0.85102	1.254	1204
0.5556	0.86555	1.366	1227	0.85640	1.120	1196
0.5999	0.87015	1.240	1221	0.86075	1.024	1190
0.6554	0.87604	1.098	1213	0.86633	0.915	1182
0.6995	0.88084	0.998	1207	0.87086	0.837	1177
0.7554	0.88706	0.883	1200	0.87671	0.748	1169
0.7999	0.89214	0.801	1194	0.88147	0.683	1163
0.8555	0.89865	0.710	1186	0.88756	0.611	1156
0.8999	0.90395	0.644	1180	0.89251	0.558	1150
0.9555	0.91088	0.571	1173	0.89896	0.499	1143
1	0.91632	0.518	1167	0.90400	0.456	1137
	EA (1) + heptane-1-ol (2)					
0	0.81871	5.725	1331	0.81251	4.322	1295
0.0555	0.82242	5.010	1321	0.81616	3.815	1286
0.0998	0.82554	4.504	1314	0.81912	3.453	1278
0.1554	0.82957	3.941	1304	0.82298	3.047	1269
0.2000	0.83293	3.541	1296	0.82619	2.756	1262
0.2555	0.83726	3.098	1287	0.83031	2.433	1253
0.2999	0.84085	2.785	1280	0.83373	2.201	1245
0.3556	0.84551	2.436	1270	0.83815	1.942	1236
0.4000	0.84937	2.190	1263	0.84179	1.758	1229
0.4554	0.85437	1.916	1254	0.84651	1.552	1220
0.5000	0.85853	1.722	1246	0.85041	1.404	1213
0.5552	0.86390	1.508	1237	0.85546	1.240	1205
0.5998	0.86839	1.355	1230	0.85967	1.121	1198
0.6550	0.87416	1.186	1221	0.86506	0.990	1189
0.7000	0.87906	1.065	1214	0.86961	0.895	1182
0.7550	0.88526	0.933	1205	0.87538	0.791	1174
0.7999	0.89053	0.837	1198	0.88027	0.715	1167
0.8551	0.89726	0.734	1189	0.88649	0.632	1159
0.8999	0.90294	0.659	1182	0.89172	0.571	1152

Table-2 (contd.)

0.9554	0.91038	0.576	1174	0.89857	0.504	1144
1	0.91632	0.518	1167	0.90400	0.456	1137
EA (1) + octane-1-ol (2)						
0	0.82160	7.362	1351	0.81453	5.520	1319
0.0555	0.82479	6.354	1340	0.81770	4.807	1308
0.0999	0.82750	5.647	1331	0.82029	4.303	1300
0.1555	0.83104	4.872	1321	0.82370	3.746	1289
0.1998	0.83398	4.332	1312	0.82654	3.354	1280
0.2556	0.83788	3.736	1301	0.83028	2.918	1270
0.2997	0.84111	3.322	1293	0.83337	2.614	1262
0.3551	0.84534	2.868	1283	0.83743	2.277	1251
0.3999	0.84895	2.546	1274	0.84086	2.036	1243
0.4551	0.85360	2.200	1264	0.84528	1.774	1233
0.4998	0.85754	1.954	1256	0.84900	1.587	1225
0.5555	0.86272	1.685	1245	0.85392	1.381	1215
0.5998	0.86704	1.498	1237	0.85799	1.237	1207
0.6550	0.87268	1.294	1227	0.86332	1.078	1197
0.6999	0.87752	1.148	1219	0.86787	0.963	1189
0.7555	0.88383	0.991	1210	0.87378	0.839	1179
0.7998	0.88912	0.881	1202	0.87872	0.751	1171
0.8554	0.89611	0.760	1192	0.88525	0.654	1162
0.8999	0.90201	0.675	1184	0.89075	0.585	1154
0.9550	0.90980	0.584	1175	0.89802	0.510	1145
1	0.91632	0.518	1167	0.90400	0.456	1137
EA (1) + decane-1-ol (2)						
0	0.82630	11.793	1388	0.81944	8.116	1353
0.0554	0.82873	9.917	1375	0.82188	6.918	1340
0.0999	0.83083	8.630	1364	0.82389	6.087	1330
0.1553	0.83362	7.257	1351	0.82659	5.189	1317
0.1998	0.83599	6.315	1341	0.82889	4.565	1307
0.2556	0.83917	5.305	1328	0.83194	3.888	1294
0.2999	0.84186	4.619	1318	0.83452	3.422	1284
0.3554	0.84546	3.883	1305	0.83796	2.916	1272
0.4000	0.84854	3.378	1295	0.84089	2.565	1262
0.4555	0.85264	2.840	1283	0.84479	2.187	1250
0.4999	0.85615	2.472	1273	0.84810	1.924	1240
0.5554	0.86086	2.078	1260	0.85255	1.640	1228
0.5999	0.86490	1.808	1251	0.85635	1.442	1219
0.6555	0.87033	1.520	1239	0.86144	1.229	1207
0.6999	0.87498	1.323	1229	0.86579	1.082	1198
0.7556	0.88126	1.112	1217	0.87165	0.921	1186
0.7999	0.88666	0.968	1208	0.87667	0.811	1177
0.8555	0.89398	0.814	1197	0.88344	0.691	1166
0.8999	0.90031	0.708	1187	0.88929	0.608	1157
0.9555	0.90899	0.595	1176	0.89734	0.518	1146
1	0.91632	0.518	1167	0.90400	0.456	1137

The excess molar volumes, V^E , of the solutions of molar compositions x were calculated from the densities of the pure liquids and their mixtures according to the following equation,

$$V^E (\text{cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}) = [x_1 M_1 + x_2 M_2 / \rho_{12} - [(x_1 M_1 / \rho_1) + (x_2 M_2 / \rho_2)]] \quad (1)$$

where ρ_{12} is the density of the mixture and x_1 , M_1 , ρ_1 , and x_2 , M_2 , ρ_2 are the mole fraction, the molecular weight, and the density of pure components 1 and 2, respectively. The first term on the right hand side of above eq. (1) represents the actual molar volume, V , of the solution and the second represents the molar volume it would occupy if the mixture behaved ideally. In general, while these two molar volumes are similar in size (usually larger than $100 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) their difference is usually smaller by two to three orders of magnitude and thus may carry a significantly larger error.

The viscosity deviations ($\Delta\eta$) were calculated using equation,

$$\Delta\eta (\text{mPa.s}) = \eta_{12} - x_1 \eta_1 - x_2 \eta_2 \quad (2)$$

where η_{12} is the viscosity of the mixture and x_1 , x_2 and η_1 , η_2 are the mole fractions and the viscosity of pure components 1 and 2 respectively¹². The excess isentropic compressibility, κ_s^E , were obtained using the relation,

$$\kappa_s^E / (\text{TPa}^{-1}) = \kappa_s - \kappa_s^{\text{id}} \quad (3)$$

where κ_s is the isentropic compressibility and was calculated using the Laplace relation,

$$\kappa_s = (1/u^2 \rho) \quad (4)$$

and κ_s^{id} was calculated from the relation,

$$\kappa_s^{\text{id}} = \sum \phi_i [\kappa_{s,i} + T V_i^{\circ} (\alpha_i^{\circ})^2 / C_{p,i}] - [T (\sum x_i V_i^{\circ}) (\sum \phi_i \alpha_i^{\circ})^2 / \sum x_i C_{p,i}] \quad (5)$$

where ϕ_i is the ideal state volume fraction of the component i in the mixture stated and is defined by the relation,

$$\phi_i = x_i V_i^{\circ} / (\sum x_i V_i^{\circ}) \quad (6)$$

T is the temperature, and $\kappa_{s,i}$, V_i° , α_i° , and $C_{p,i}$ are the isentropic compressibility, molar volume, coefficient of isobaric thermal expansion, and molar heat capacity respectively, for pure component i . α_i° is calculated from the measured densities by the relation,

$$\alpha = [(\rho_1 / \rho_2) - 1] / (T_2 - T_1) \quad (7)$$

The other required values were taken from literature^{13,14}.

According to Eyring and his coworkers, a sound wave in a liquid is supposed to travel with infinite velocity within a molecule and with gas kinetic velocity in inter space i.e. the available volume. Distance between surfaces of two molecules i.e. intermolecular free length (L_f) covered by a sound wave by,

$$L_f = [2Va]/Y = 2 [V_T - V]/Y \quad (8)$$

where Va is available volume per molecule, V_T and V are molar volumes at absolute temperature T and zero; Y is surface area per molecule.

$$V = V_T (1 - T/T_c)^{0.3} \text{ and } Y = (36\pi N V_2)^{0.3} \quad (9)$$

where T_c is critical temperature, N is Avogadro's no.

V for pure liquids calculated on assumption of spherical molecules. For pure liquids L_f can be given by Jacobson's relation,

$$L_f = K/u\rho^{1/2} \quad (10)$$

where u and ρ are experimental values of speed of sound and density,

$K = ((93.875 + 0.375T) \times 10^{-8})$ is Jacobson's constant which is temperature dependent in a mixture¹⁵, intermolecular free length is obtained by extending definition of L_f as

$$L_f (\text{mix}) = 2[Vm - (x_1 V_1 + x_2 V_2)]/[x_1 Y_1 + x_2 Y_2] \quad (11)$$

where subscripts 1 and 2 refer to pure components of mixture and x is mole fraction.

Va is available volume per molecule can be obtained by a relation,

$$Va = Vm (1 - u/u_{\infty}) \quad (12)$$

where $u_{\infty} = 1600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The excess molar volume, deviation in viscosity, deviation in isentropic compressibility, intermolecular free length and available volume for binary liquid mixtures of ethyl acrylate with higher primary alkane-1-ol are listed in Table 3. The excess molar volumes, deviations in viscosity and excess isentropic compressibility were fitted to Redlich-Kister equation of the type,

$$Y = x_1 x_2 \sum_i^n a_i (x_1 - x_2)^i \quad (13)$$

where Y is either V^E or $\Delta\eta$ or κ_s^E and n is the degree of polynomial. Coefficient a_i was obtained by fitting eq. (13)

Table 3. Excess molar volumes, V^E , viscosity deviation, $\Delta\eta$, deviation in isentropic compressibility, κ_s^E , intermolecular free length, L_f , and available volume, V_a of ethyl acrylate (1) + alkane-1-ol (2) at $T = (298.15 \text{ and } 308.15) \text{ K}$

x_1	$T=298.15\text{K}$					$T=308.15\text{K}$				
	V^E ($\text{cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	$\Delta\eta$ ($\text{mPa}\cdot\text{s}$)	κ_s^E (TPa^{-1})	L_f (10^{12} cm)	V_a ($\text{m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	V^E ($\text{cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	$\Delta\eta$ ($\text{mPa}\cdot\text{s}$)	κ_s^E (TPa^{-1})	L_f (10^{12} cm)	V_a ($\text{m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)
EA (1) + hexane-1-ol (2)										
0	0.000	0.000	0	0.530	23.027	0.000	0.000	0	0.554	25.765
0.055	0.062	-0.295	1	0.532	23.499	0.048	-0.199	1	0.556	26.227
0.0998	0.119	-0.492	2	0.533	23.915	0.089	-0.332	2	0.558	26.558
0.1555	0.175	-0.688	3	0.535	24.369	0.131	-0.465	3	0.560	27.002
0.1998	0.214	-0.809	3	0.537	24.694	0.160	-0.549	3	0.562	27.396
0.2555	0.255	-0.921	4	0.538	25.130	0.190	-0.627	4	0.564	27.823
0.2999	0.282	-0.983	5	0.540	25.440	0.210	-0.671	4	0.565	28.126
0.3555	0.308	-1.030	5	0.541	25.858	0.229	-0.705	5	0.567	28.535
0.3999	0.323	-1.044	5	0.543	26.228	0.240	-0.716	5	0.569	28.824
0.4555	0.334	-1.037	6	0.544	26.552	0.248	-0.713	5	0.570	29.141
0.4999	0.339	-1.013	6	0.546	26.835	0.252	-0.698	5	0.572	29.417
0.5556	0.332	-0.962	6	0.548	27.213	0.246	-0.665	5	0.574	29.789
0.5999	0.322	-0.908	6	0.549	27.479	0.239	-0.629	5	0.575	30.052
0.6554	0.302	-0.823	5	0.550	27.839	0.224	-0.572	5	0.577	30.406
0.6995	0.280	-0.744	5	0.552	28.091	0.207	-0.518	5	0.578	30.582
0.7554	0.245	-0.631	4	0.553	28.359	0.181	-0.440	4	0.580	30.917
0.7999	0.211	-0.532	4	0.554	28.594	0.156	-0.371	4	0.582	31.150
0.8555	0.161	-0.397	3	0.556	28.914	0.118	-0.278	3	0.583	31.396
0.8999	0.115	-0.282	2	0.557	29.134	0.084	-0.197	2	0.584	31.615
0.9555	0.038	-0.129	1	0.558	29.361	0.024	-0.090	1	0.586	31.840
1	0.000	0.000	0	0.559	29.569	0.000	0.000	0	0.587	32.049
EA (1) + heptane-1-ol (2)										
0	0.000	0.000	0	0.519	23.862	0.000	0.000	0	0.544	27.262
0.0555	0.087	-0.426	2	0.522	24.448	0.057	-0.293	2	0.547	27.726
0.0998	0.142	-0.701	4	0.523	24.813	0.107	-0.483	4	0.549	28.155
0.1554	0.205	-0.975	5	0.526	25.356	0.157	-0.674	5	0.552	28.581
0.2000	0.249	-1.143	7	0.528	25.773	0.191	-0.793	7	0.554	28.889
0.2555	0.295	-1.296	8	0.531	26.190	0.228	-0.902	8	0.556	29.278
0.2999	0.325	-1.379	9	0.532	26.492	0.252	-0.961	9	0.559	29.640
0.3556	0.354	-1.437	10	0.535	26.950	0.275	-1.005	10	0.561	29.988
0.4000	0.371	-1.453	11	0.537	27.220	0.288	-1.018	11	0.563	30.236
0.4554	0.382	-1.437	12	0.539	27.558	0.297	-1.010	11	0.566	30.547
0.5000	0.386	-1.400	12	0.541	27.874	0.302	-0.985	12	0.568	30.763
0.5552	0.379	-1.326	12	0.544	28.172	0.295	-0.936	12	0.570	30.957
0.5998	0.368	-1.247	12	0.545	28.375	0.286	-0.882	11	0.572	31.142
0.6550	0.345	-1.128	11	0.547	28.633	0.268	-0.799	11	0.574	31.377
0.7000	0.320	-1.015	11	0.549	28.801	0.248	-0.721	10	0.576	31.527
0.7550	0.280	-0.861	10	0.551	29.019	0.217	-0.612	9	0.578	31.650
0.7999	0.241	-0.722	8	0.553	29.155	0.186	-0.515	8	0.580	31.770
0.8551	0.184	-0.539	7	0.555	29.330	0.141	-0.385	6	0.582	31.853
0.8999	0.131	-0.381	5	0.556	29.434	0.100	-0.272	5	0.584	31.943

Table-3 (contd.)

0.9554	0.044	-0.174	2	0.558	29.491	0.028	-0.125	2	0.586	31.983
1	0.000	0.000	0	0.559	29.569	0.000	0.000	0	0.587	32.049
EA (1) + octane-1-ol (2)										
0	0.000	0.000	0	0.510	24.668	0.000	0.000	0	0.533	28.080
0.0555	0.094	-0.628	3	0.514	25.329	0.063	-0.432	3	0.537	28.693
0.0999	0.154	-1.031	5	0.516	25.848	0.119	-0.711	5	0.539	29.080
0.1555	0.223	-1.425	8	0.519	26.343	0.175	-0.987	8	0.543	29.627
0.1998	0.271	-1.663	10	0.522	26.810	0.214	-1.154	10	0.546	30.357
0.2556	0.321	-1.877	12	0.525	27.329	0.255	-1.307	12	0.549	30.439
0.2997	0.354	-1.988	14	0.527	27.649	0.282	-1.388	14	0.551	30.724
0.3551	0.386	-2.063	15	0.530	28.017	0.307	-1.445	16	0.555	31.136
0.3999	0.403	-2.078	16	0.532	28.365	0.322	-1.459	17	0.557	31.362
0.4551	0.416	-2.048	17	0.535	28.668	0.332	-1.441	18	0.560	31.621
0.4998	0.420	-1.988	18	0.537	28.878	0.338	-1.402	18	0.563	31.797
0.5555	0.413	-1.875	18	0.540	29.191	0.330	-1.326	19	0.566	31.984
0.5998	0.401	-1.759	18	0.543	29.351	0.321	-1.246	18	0.568	32.112
0.6550	0.377	-1.585	17	0.545	29.521	0.301	-1.125	18	0.571	32.241
0.6999	0.350	-1.423	17	0.547	29.620	0.279	-1.012	17	0.573	32.308
0.7555	0.307	-1.200	15	0.549	29.642	0.244	-0.855	15	0.576	32.366
0.7998	0.264	-1.007	13	0.551	29.697	0.210	-0.719	14	0.578	32.389
0.8554	0.203	-0.747	11	0.554	29.729	0.160	-0.534	11	0.581	32.307
0.8999	0.145	-0.528	8	0.556	29.727	0.113	-0.378	8	0.583	32.274
0.9550	0.056	-0.243	4	0.558	29.627	0.035	-0.174	4	0.585	32.134
1	0.000	0.000	0	0.559	29.569	0.000	0.000	0	0.587	32.049
EA (1) + decane-1-ol (2)										
0	0.000	0.000	0	0.495	25.381	0.000	0.000	0	0.518	29.819
0.0554	0.109	-1.251	5	0.499	26.311	0.072	-0.773	5	0.523	30.657
0.0999	0.182	-2.037	8	0.503	27.068	0.136	-1.264	9	0.526	31.228
0.1553	0.264	-2.784	12	0.507	27.862	0.200	-1.737	13	0.530	31.936
0.1998	0.321	-3.225	16	0.510	28.396	0.244	-2.020	16	0.534	32.399
0.2556	0.381	-3.606	19	0.514	29.054	0.291	-2.270	20	0.538	32.969
0.2999	0.420	-3.793	22	0.517	29.485	0.321	-2.397	23	0.541	33.331
0.3554	0.457	-3.903	25	0.521	30.009	0.351	-2.477	26	0.545	33.665
0.4000	0.479	-3.905	27	0.524	30.332	0.368	-2.487	28	0.549	33.919
0.4555	0.494	-3.818	29	0.528	30.624	0.380	-2.441	30	0.553	34.126
0.4999	0.499	-3.685	30	0.531	30.843	0.386	-2.363	31	0.556	34.278
0.5554	0.491	-3.453	31	0.535	31.095	0.377	-2.222	32	0.560	34.353
0.5999	0.477	-3.221	31	0.537	31.118	0.366	-2.078	32	0.563	34.310
0.6555	0.447	-2.882	30	0.541	31.149	0.343	-1.866	31	0.567	34.260
0.6999	0.415	-2.579	29	0.544	31.156	0.318	-1.673	30	0.570	34.118
0.7556	0.364	-2.162	27	0.547	31.057	0.278	-1.407	28	0.573	33.941
0.7999	0.314	-1.806	24	0.549	30.879	0.239	-1.178	25	0.576	33.701
0.8555	0.240	-1.334	20	0.552	30.577	0.182	-0.872	20	0.579	33.322
0.8999	0.172	-0.939	15	0.555	30.375	0.129	-0.615	15	0.582	32.985
0.9555	0.066	-0.425	7	0.557	29.943	0.039	-0.279	7	0.585	32.478
1	0.000	0.000	0	0.559	29.569	0.000	0.000	0	0.587	32.049

to experimental results using a least-squares regression method. In each case, the optimum number of coefficients is ascertained from an examination of the variation in standard deviation (σ).

σ was calculated using the relation,

$$\sigma(Y) = \left[\frac{\sum (Y_{\text{expt}} - Y_{\text{calc}})^2}{N-n} \right]^{1/2} \quad (14)$$

where N is the number of data points and n is the number of coefficients¹³. The calculated values of the coefficients a_i along with the standard deviations (σ) are given in Table 4.

Several relations have been proposed to evaluate the dynamic viscosity η of liquid mixtures and these are classified according to the number of adjustable parameters used to account for the deviation from some average. An attempt has been made to check the suitability of the equation for experimental data fits by taking into account the number of empirical adjustable coefficients. The equations of Grunberg-Nissan, Tamura and Kurata have one adjustable parameter. Grunberg-Nissan provided the following empirical equation containing one adjustable parameter. The expression is,

$$\ln \eta_{12} = x_1 \ln \eta_1 + x_2 \ln \eta_2 + x_1 x_2 G_{12} \quad (15)$$

where G_{12} is a parameter proportional to the interchange energy.

Table 4. Adjustable parameters of eqs. (13) and (14) for the mathematical representation of excess functions for binary liquid mixture of ethyl acrylate (1) + alkane-1-ol (2) at $T = (298.15 \text{ and } 308.15) \text{ K}$

	$T \text{ (K)}$	a_0	a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4	σ
EA (1) + hexane-1-ol (2)							
$V^E \text{ (cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}\text{)}$	298.15	1.3275	0.0439	0.3204	-0.1904	-0.7514	0.00523
	308.15	0.9821	0.0618	0.2936	-0.2517	-0.6700	0.00516
$\Delta\eta \text{ (mPa.s)}$	298.15	-4.0500	1.4143	-0.3893	0.0911	-0.0060	0.00035
	308.15	-2.7925	0.9115	-0.2427	0.0425	0.0154	0.00037
$\kappa_s^E \text{ (TPa}^{-1}\text{)}$	298.15	9.7726	1.3401	12.1415	-2.6128	-16.1596	0.41729
	308.15	8.1066	1.3575	11.0503	-2.7696	-22.3158	0.43694
EA (1) + heptane-1-ol (2)							
$V^E \text{ (cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}\text{)}$	298.15	1.5226	0.1110	0.2739	-0.4604	-0.5484	0.00681
	308.15	1.1762	0.0666	0.3815	-0.2827	-0.8428	0.00646
$\Delta\eta \text{ (mPa.s)}$	298.15	-5.5996	2.1393	-0.6119	0.1510	-0.0586	0.00046
	308.15	-3.9414	1.4192	-0.3931	0.0845	-0.0110	0.00033
$\kappa_s^E \text{ (TPa}^{-1}\text{)}$	298.15	17.4144	10.2182	10.9431	-10.7901	-12.1668	0.40886
	308.15	15.7219	5.0024	9.7331	-6.4202	-26.7193	0.44118
EA (1) + octane-1-ol (2)							
$V^E \text{ (cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}\text{)}$	298.15	1.6647	0.0812	0.2133	-0.3439	-0.4121	0.00522
	308.15	1.3155	0.0687	0.4354	-0.2615	-0.9328	0.00678
$\Delta\eta \text{ (mPa.s)}$	298.15	-7.9494	3.3205	-1.0856	0.2942	-0.0438	0.00032
	308.15	-5.6073	2.2173	-0.6695	0.1642	-0.0385	0.00027
$\kappa_s^E \text{ (TPa}^{-1}\text{)}$	298.15	22.3283	12.6033	4.8396	-11.6714	-8.4208	0.42764
	308.15	16.8106	11.7003	17.1934	-11.6787	-27.1023	0.41004
EA (1) + decane-1-ol (2)							
$V^E \text{ (cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}\text{)}$	298.15	1.9787	0.0985	0.2318	-0.4039	-0.4738	0.00550
	308.15	1.5030	0.0815	0.4929	-0.3185	-1.0606	0.00769
$\Delta\eta \text{ (mPa.s)}$	298.15	-14.7384	7.0946	-2.6375	0.8462	-0.2441	0.00095
	308.15	-9.4514	4.2371	-1.4541	0.4356	-0.1340	0.00083
$\kappa_s^E \text{ (TPa}^{-1}\text{)}$	298.15	24.6307	18.6491	12.3198	0.1847	-10.8869	0.37209
	308.15	21.6000	19.9941	9.8113	-7.4843	-15.0861	0.25579

Tamura and Kurata developed expression for viscosity of binary mixtures as,

$$\eta = x_1\phi_1\eta_1 + x_2\phi_2\eta_2 + 2(x_1x_2\phi_1\phi_2)^{1/2}T_{12} \quad (16)$$

where T_{12} is the interaction parameter, ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 are the volume fractions.

McAllister's multibody interaction model was widely used to correlate kinematic viscosity (ν) data. The two parameter McAllister equation based on Eyring's theory of absolute reaction rates, taken into account interactions of both like and unlike molecules by a two dimensional three body model. The three body model was defined by the relation,

$$\begin{aligned} \ln \nu = & x_1^3 \ln \nu_1 + x_2^3 \ln \nu_2 + 3x_1^2x_2 \ln Z_{12} \\ & + 3x_1x_2^2 \ln Z_{21} - \ln [x_1 + (x_2M_2/M_1)] \\ & + 3x_1^2x_2 \ln [(2/3) + (M_2/3M_1)] \\ & + 3x_1x_2^2 \ln [(1/3) + (2M_2/3M_1)] \\ & + x_2^3 \ln (M_2/M_1) \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

Similarly, the four body model was defined by the relation,

$$\begin{aligned} \ln \nu = & x_1^4 \ln \nu_1 + 4x_1^3x_2 \ln Z_{1112} + 6x_1^2x_2^2 \ln Z_{1122} \\ & + 4x_1x_2^3 \ln Z_{2221} + x_2^4 \ln \nu_2 \\ & - \ln [x_1 + x_2 (M_2/M_1)] \\ & + 4x_1^3x_2 \ln [(3 + M_2/M_1)/4] \\ & + 6x_1^2x_2^2 \ln [1 + M_2/M_1)/2] \\ & + 4x_1x_2^3 \ln [(1 + 3M_2/M_1)/4] \\ & + x_2^4 \ln (M_2/M_1) \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

where Z_{12} , Z_{21} , Z_{1112} , Z_{1122} and Z_{2221} are model parameters and M_i and ν_i are the molecular mass and kinematic viscosity of pure component i .

To perform a numerical comparison of the correlating capability of above eqs. (15 to 18) we have calculated the standard percentage deviation ($\sigma\%$) using the relation,

$$\sigma \% = [1/(\eta_{\text{expt}} - k) \times \sum (100 (\eta_{\text{expt}} - \eta_{\text{calc}})/\eta_{\text{expt}})^2]^{1/2} \quad (19)$$

where k represents the number of numerical coefficients in the respective equations.

The terms G_{12} , T_{12} , Z_{12} , Z_{21} , Z_{1112} , Z_{1122} and Z_{2221} in the above eqs. (15, 16, 17 and 18) have been considered as adjustable parameters and were estimated by a non-linear regression analysis based on a least-squares method. These are presented with their standard percentage deviation ($\sigma\%$) in Table 5. The eq. (15) is particularly selected because the characteristic constant parameter G_{12} allows for the positive and negative deviations from the additivity rule¹⁶.

Recently Jouyban and Acree proposed a model for correlating the density and viscosity of liquid mixtures at various temperatures. The proposed equation is,

$$\begin{aligned} \ln y_{mT} = & f_1 \ln y_{1T} + f_2 \ln y_{2T} \\ & + f_1f_2 \sum [A_j (f_1 - f_2)^j/T] \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

where y_{mT} , y_{1T} and y_{2T} is density or viscosity of the mixture and solvents 1 and 2 at temperature T , respectively, f_1 and f_2 are the volume fractions of solvents in case of density, and mole fraction in case of viscosity,

Table 5. Adjustable parameters of eqs. (15, 16, 17, 18 and 19) for the mathematical representation of excess functions for binary liquid mixture of ethyl acrylate (1) + alkane-1-ol (2) at $T = (298.15 \text{ and } 308.15) \text{ K}$

T (K)	G_{12}	σ	T_{12}	σ	Z_{12}	Z_{21}	σ	Z_{1112}	Z_{1122}	Z_{2221}	σ
EA (1) + hexane-1-ol (2)											
298.15	-0.001	0.030	0.354	10.560	1.224	2.634	0.030	1.009	1.779	3.183	0.869
308.15	-0.001	0.029	0.436	8.802	1.033	2.106	0.026	0.863	1.461	2.512	1.150
EA (1) + heptane-1-ol (2)											
298.15	-0.001	0.036	-0.071	17.120	1.324	3.061	0.048	1.068	1.870	3.757	1.837
308.15	-0.001	0.025	0.141	13.512	1.119	2.451	0.027	0.916	1.535	2.973	0.559
EA (1) + octane-1-ol (2)											
298.15	-0.001	0.022	-0.759	27.300	1.452	3.625	0.020	1.147	1.991	4.544	4.090
308.15	-0.001	0.021	-0.330	21.739	1.223	2.895	0.027	0.979	1.637	3.576	1.325
EA (1) + decane-1-ol (2)											
298.15	0.000	0.024	-3.027	58.839	1.730	4.988	0.040	1.304	2.268	6.478	11.515
308.15	-0.001	0.036	-1.616	43.010	1.414	3.758	0.039	1.089	1.784	4.778	4.765

and A_j are the model constants. The Jouyban-Acree model was not previously applied to ultrasonic velocity measurements, we extend the Jouyban-Acree model eq. (20) to ultrasonic velocity of the liquid mixtures with f as the mole fraction and again apply eq. (21) for correlating ability of the model. The correlating ability of the Jouyban-Acree model was tested by calculating the average percentage deviation (APD) between the experimental and calculated density, viscosity and ultrasonic velocity as,

$$\text{APD} = (100/N) \sum [(|y_{\text{expt}} - y_{\text{calc}}|)/y_{\text{expt}}] \quad (21)$$

where N is the number of data points in each set. The optimum numbers of constants A_j , in each case, were determined from the examination of the average percentage deviation value. The constants A_j calculated from the least square analysis along with the average percentage deviation (APD) are presented in Table 6. The proposed model provides reasonably accurate calculations for the density, viscosity and ultrasonic velocity of binary liquid mixtures at various temperatures and the model could be used in data modeling^{17,18}.

A graphical comparison of the dependence of excess molar volume, V^E , at 298.15 and 308.15 K for the binary mixtures of ethyl acrylate with each alkane-1-ol is given in Figs. 1 and 2. Excess molar volumes, which are a measure of the deviations of the actual property from the

property if the system behaves ideally, gives information on molecular interactions between the component molecules of the mixture and are influenced by effects such as (i) differences in shape and size of the component molecules, (ii) reorientation of the component molecules in the mixture and (iii) intermolecular interactions^{19,20}. The curves in Figs. 1 and 2 reveals that the values of V^E , are positive over the entire mole fraction of ethyl acrylate for all four binary liquid systems studied and they follow the sequence : hexane-1-ol < heptane-1-ol < octane-1-ol < decane-1-ol. The maxima for both these figures of variation of excess molar volumes were found at 0.4999 mole fraction. These two figures show that; as the temperature increases, V^E values increases for all the mixtures over the entire mole fraction range and, thereby, suggest a decrease in the strength of interactions between the component molecules. Similarly, as the size of the alkyl group increases from hexane-1-ol to decane-1-ol, the steric hindrance also increases, resulting in a increased interactions between ethyl acrylate and alkane-1-ol molecules, and hence, the strength of the $n \dots \pi$ interactions should follow above mentioned order.

A graphical comparison of the dependence of deviation in viscosity, $\Delta\eta$, at 298.15 and 308.15 K over entire range of mole fraction for the binary mixtures of ethyl acrylate with each alkane-1-ol is given in Figs. 3 and 4.

Table 6. Adjustable parameters of eqs. (20 and 21) for the mathematical representation of excess functions for binary liquid mixture of ethyl acrylate (1) + alkane-1-ol (2) at $T = (298.15 \text{ and } 308.15) \text{ K}$

	a_0	a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4	σ	APD
	EA (1) + hexane-1-ol (2)						
ρ (g cm ⁻³)	-5.3782	-0.4643	-0.8716	0.6475	1.9585	1.8993	0.0270
η (mPa.s)	-0.2974	-0.0551	0.4016	-1.1276	-1.8522	1.8644	0.0208
u (m s ⁻¹)	0.1404	-0.5752	-1.8404	1.5164	2.8805	1253.938	0.0204
	EA (1) + heptane-1-ol (2)						
ρ (g cm ⁻³)	-9.7453	-1.3099	-1.0865	0.8568	2.0444	2.7448	0.0277
η (mPa.s)	-0.3653	0.5286	2.5132	-2.4097	-5.2264	2.2177	0.0258
u (m s ⁻¹)	0.0930	-0.3203	-2.2084	0.9658	4.1052	1265.4785	0.0203
	EA (1) + octane-1-ol (2)						
ρ (g.cm ⁻³)	-13.1672	-2.3792	-1.2754	0.7580	1.9006	3.4139	0.0256
η (mPa.s)	-0.2022	-0.6441	-0.2167	0.6273	0.0166	2.6572	0.0193
u (m s ⁻¹)	0.0034	-1.0261	-1.0136	2.5006	2.1942	1276.7302	0.0211
	EA (1) + decane-1-ol (2)						
ρ (g cm ⁻³)	-18.2994	-4.9176	-2.2233	0.6837	2.1395	4.4405	0.0362
η (mPa.s)	-0.2871	0.2529	2.1928	-2.2302	-4.3994	3.7050	0.0227
u (m s ⁻¹)	0.0598	-0.8037	-0.9323	1.4867	1.6833	1293.6859	0.0186

Fig. 1. Variation of excess molar volumes with ethyl acrylate mole fraction for binary mixtures of ethyl acrylate + alkane-1-ols at 298.15 K : (♦) hexane-1-ol; (■) heptane-1-ol; (▲) octane-1-ol; (×) decane-1-ol.

Fig. 4. Variation of deviation of viscosity with ethyl acrylate mole fraction for binary mixtures of ethyl acrylate + alkane-1-ols at 308.15 K : (♦) hexane-1-ol; (■) heptane-1-ol; (▲) octane-1-ol; (×) decane-1-ol.

Fig. 2. Variation of excess molar volumes with ethyl acrylate mole fraction for binary mixtures of ethyl acrylate + alkane-1-ols at 308.15 K : (♦) hexane-1-ol; (■) heptane-1-ol; (▲) octane-1-ol; (×) decane-1-ol.

Fig. 5. Variation of excess isentropic compressibility with ethyl acrylate mole fraction for binary mixtures of ethyl acrylate + alkane-1-ols at 298.15 K : (♦) hexane-1-ol; (■) heptane-1-ol; (▲) octane-1-ol; (×) decane-1-ol.

Fig. 3. Variation of deviation of viscosity with ethyl acrylate mole fraction for binary mixtures of ethyl acrylate + alkane-1-ols at 298.15 K : (♦) hexane-1-ol; (■) heptane-1-ol; (▲) octane-1-ol; (×) decane-1-ol.

Fig. 6. Variation of excess isentropic compressibility with ethyl acrylate mole fraction for binary mixtures of ethyl acrylate + alkane-1-ols at 308.15 K : (♦) hexane-1-ol; (■) heptane-1-ol; (▲) octane-1-ol; (×) decane-1-ol.

Values of deviation in viscosity decrease with increase in temperature in all cases. Maximum magnitude of such values for mixtures containing various alkane-1-ols de-

crease in order higher to lower number of carbon atoms in it. Similar type of behavior has been reported for alkane-1-ols i.e. negative magnitude of $\Delta\eta$ at equimolar

compositions increases in order higher to lower number of carbon atoms in alkane-1-ols.

A graphical variation of excess isentropic compressibility, κ_s^E , at both the temperatures over whole range of composition for all binary liquid mixtures shows the positive nature in Figs. 5 and 6. This type nature of graphs were found due to, (i) hydrogen bonded aggregates of alkane-1-ols breaks up progressively with the addition of another combining component in the mixture and (ii) weak interactions between unlike molecules. The two factors contribute to increase in free length and negative deviation in ultrasonic velocity and positive deviation in excess isentropic compressibility.

Conclusions :

Disruption of hydrogen bonds in alkane-1-ols associates and dipole-dipole repulsive interactions are mainly responsible for the observed positive excess molar volumes. If one liquid of higher viscosity mixes with liquid of lower viscosity to form a binary mixture, usually viscosity deviations are negative. Excess isentropic compressibility increases with increase in chain length of alkane-1-ols, which is due to increase in steric effect.

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